

DIGITAL PEDAGOGY AND STUDENTS - PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING DIGITAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the author, as in all developed countries in the world, continues the formation of the post-industrial information society, its distinctive feature is information and communication technologies (ICT) in the material sphere of the social center, in the sphere of education and science. based on the application of information, the issues of transfer to the sphere of information acquisition, processing, delivery, storage, presentation and use are highlighted.

Key words: information society, digital technologies, quality of education, object, network, concept, social work, parameter, social work, information and communication, international research.

Digital technologies are actively introduced into the education system in our country is being done. In this regard, the PF-According to Decree No. 5712, Uzbekistan will be among the first 70 in 2021, 60 in 2025, and 60 in 2030 in the PISA (The Program for International Student Assessment) international student assessment program and it is planned to be included among the first 30 advanced countries. With the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 997 of December 8, 2018 "On measures to organize international research in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system", Uzbekistan The "National Center for the Implementation of International Researches on the Evaluation of the Quality of Education" was established under the State Inspection of Education Quality Control under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic. Uzbekistan Digitization in the digital world in the decree of the President of the Republic of October 5, 2020 No. PF 6079 "On approval of the strategy of Digital Uzbekistan 2030 and measures for its implementation", development of digital technologies, consideration of new projects in the field of digital economy, and programs for the development of digital education is being implemented.

“Digital technologies - Internet of Things (IoT). One of the main technologies based on digital information is the Internet of Things. It is common for many household appliances to be connected to the electrical network, but gradually more and more objects of the physical world are connected to the Internet, which allows collecting

information and even controlling these objects remotely. In fact, a virtual copy of a physical object appears on the Internet, containing various parameters of the object and the outside world, and allowing to control the object via the Internet.”[1] As an example of the Internet of Things, a device such as a projector in a movie theater sends a signal to the technical support service about a detected fault and a list of parts that need to be replaced as part of unscheduled maintenance. . Digital technologies - augmented reality (AR). The most promising is augmented reality technology, which allows adding objects from the virtual world to the real world. Imagine walking down the street and seeing more information about things and people around you. Examples of augmented reality already exist and are actively used, in some amusement parks you can already see signs that show the connections between objects in the physical world and the virtual world. Games with elements of augmented reality are actively spreading, clothing stores have virtual windows and fitting rooms, augmented reality is already being tested in cars. At the same time, there are issues that need to be resolved in order to actively use augmented reality technologies. For example, the accuracy of geolocation tools is still insufficient, or the computer vision technologies for connecting objects of the physical world with their virtual counterparts are imperfect. However, it is safe to say that in the near future this technology may be associated with breakthroughs.

The opening of Wi-Fi zones and IT parks will greatly contribute to the development of the digital education system. It will be possible to increase the ability of educators to work with digital technologies and organize various open courses via the Internet. This, in turn, helps educators to work harder on themselves and increase the quality of education due to competition. In addition, when digital technologies and the introduction of artificial intelligence technology are used to detect tax evasion, prevent fraud, analyze data and automate repetitive processes, and increase transparency, large volumes of data - And big data provides an opportunity to store and process a large amount of data received by tax authorities, to better predict revenues and to improve the exchange of documents between taxpayers and tax authorities. “Adoption of digital technologies is happening faster than any other innovation in human history: in just two decades, digital technologies have managed to cover almost 50% of the population of developing countries and transform societies with their help. For example, advanced technologies based on the use of artificial intelligence in the healthcare sector are helping to save human lives, detect diseases and increase life expectancy. In the field of education, the provision of virtual learning environments and distance learning has allowed students to participate in programs that they would not have otherwise. In addition, through the

use of blockchain-based systems, the use of public services will be convenient, the institutions that provide them will be more accountable, and the processes will be less bureaucratic due to the use of artificial intelligence. Big data can also lead to more flexible and accurate policies and programs. Below we will touch on some digital technologies: cloud technologies are data processing technologies that provide computer resources as an online service to the Internet user. The current state of the education system is characterized by the increasing role of non-traditional educational technologies. Learning by the learner with their help is much faster than with traditional technologies. These technologies change the nature of knowledge development, acquisition and distribution, deepening and expanding the content of the studied subjects, quickly updating it, using more effective teaching methods, and also significantly expanding the opportunity for education for everyone. will give. We answer the question of what digital technology is as follows: it is a modern form of economic management. a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing serve as the main factor of production and management. Using the obtained results in practice makes it possible to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of management. For example, various automatic production processes, 3D technology, cloud technologies. it is possible to mention the provision of remote medical services, the production and delivery of products with the help of smart technologies, the processes of storing and selling various goods. In this article, we will focus instead on digitization in the education system.”[2]

We will answer the question of what is digital technology as follows: it is a modern form of economic management, in which a large set of data in digital form and the process of processing them serve as the main factor of production and management. “Using the obtained results in practice makes it possible to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of management. For example, various automatic production processes, 3D technology, cloud technologies. it is possible to mention the provision of remote medical services, the production and delivery of products with the help of smart technologies, the processes of storing and selling various goods. In this article, we will focus instead on digitization in the education system.”[3] If education is provided through digital technologies, the methods of education are becoming easier for learners. In this case, multimedia, overhead projector, computer, laptop, televisions connected to the Internet, telephone lines, smart boards, and projectors play the role of educational system mediators. Training teachers with such tools ensures the improvement of the quality of education. We all know that the use of digital technologies in online classes has a good effect. For

example, we can consider online classes given on television as a type of digital education. The implementation of modern standards requires not only high qualifications and continuous professional development from the teacher, but also a creative approach to his work. "It is becoming very important for the teacher's creativity to revise and improve his experience, to be able to change and creatively use things known to everyone, to create quality innovations. The concept of creativity (lat., eng. "create" - creation, "creative" means creation when translated from English). Creativity can be called: striving for creativity, creative approach to life, constant self-critical observation and analysis. Based on the modern dictionaries of psychology and pedagogy, the teacher's creativity can be defined as the level of knowledge, feelings, communication, special activity, creative approach. Today, digital technologies are rapidly developing and require keeping up with the times in every field." [4] For example, the introduction of artificial intelligence technology helps to detect cases of tax evasion, prevent fraud, analyze data and automate existing processes, and increase transparency, while large-volume data - Big data provides an opportunity to store and process a large amount of data received by tax authorities, better predict incomes and improve the exchange of documents between taxpayers and tax authorities. In the age of digital technologies, data is the most important factor.

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